

Gender (anti)essentialist discourses and feminist tensions in the post-Yugoslav space

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Abstract

Trans rights are under attack both globally and within feminist movements. To discover the effects of various gender discourses and the direction of the feminist movement, we conducted a case study in the post-Yugoslav space. We interviewed 12 feminist activists and analyzed 13 statements from feminist organizations. Under a feminist social constructivist paradigm, we analyzed their discourse on gender and feminism and its influence on the local movements. We identified three competing feminist discourses among our interviewees: radical, moderate, and intersectional. Looking through Sara Ahmed's affect theory, we find that a broadening of the category of woman by some feminists causes fear and discomfort in others, who feel that they are losing something in the process. This has caused them to narrow their own conception of womanhood that aligns with gender essentialist discourse, and to lash out against trans women with discourses of fear. The split is also evident from a generational aspect since older generations of feminists who joined the feminist movement before or during the Yugoslav Wars generally hold a different set of values and approaches when dealing with trans issues compared to their younger colleagues who joined the movement in the last decade through the fight against a broader social injustice. We conclude that to become truly trans-inclusive, two things must happen in the post-Yugoslav feminist movement: trans voices must be heard and feminists must face their discomfort.

1. Introduction

Recently, globally popular British author J.K. Rowling positioned herself in public debates on trans people in a way that was interpreted as transphobic by many of her followers on social media (Gardner, 2021). She defended a woman who was fired for retweeting transphobic material (Noor, 2019). Rowling then published a series of tweets where she supported the claims that sex is biologically determined and that her life and identity are shaped by these (biological) experiences (ibid.). This resulted in a major backlash from her followers and fans and culminated with Judith Butler joining the debate and expressing disappointment over essentialist ideas of gender coming from within feminism (Farber, 2020).

We notice similar discourses developing within the feminist movement in the post-Yugoslav space, a region in South-Eastern Europe where different nations and ethnic groups share similar

language and history and political culture (Bilic, 2016a: 6). Feminist activists joined the debate on social media by aligning themselves with either Rowling or Butler. This sparked a major controversy among feminists in December 2020 when a feminist who supported Rowling was appointed director of Center for Women's Studies (CWS) (Kožul, 2020). Hundreds of feminist activists and various feminist organizations positioned themselves publicly *against* or in *support* of the new director of CWS (ibid.). Since 1995, CWS has run an interdisciplinary two-semester program in the field of women's studies that has educated a number of feminist activists in Croatia (Kahlina, 2006: 55; Miškovska Kajevska, 2017: 43-44; Zagreb Pride, 2020). Thus, the institution holds both historical and symbolic value across the post-Yugoslav space as the center of feminist knowledge (ibid.).

The first feminist organizations in the post-Yugoslav space were established in the 90s, just before and during the Yugoslav Wars (1991-1999). The wars resulted in forceful migrations and war crimes, including a massive number of women who were raped (Miškovska Kajevska, 2017: 6). During the wars, feminist activists organized to support war-displaced women victims of (sexual) violence and their children, and to improve the position of all women in general (ibid.). After the war, when the countries of the post-Yugoslav spaces began the process of integration into the EU, the scope of feminist concerns became focused on human rights and anti-discrimination (Bilić & Kajinić, 2016: 14-15). The EU's way of allocating grants based on particular goals led to the fragmentation of the feminist movement into organizations specialized in various areas of activist work (ibid.). In the last decade, a new generation of (feminist) activists have mobilized themselves around issues different from the ones emerging during the Yugoslav Wars. These concerns are a demand for tuition-free higher education, LGBTIQ equality and sustainable urban development (Farber., 2020; Kovačić, 2014; Vučković Juroš et al., 2020).

We are a team of queer students who are committed to social justice and queer liberation. For us, queer liberation is a life free of any type of violence and inequality based on gender and sexuality. Trans people suffer stigmatization and discrimination under patriarchy because of the rigid binary gender norms in society and assumptions that every person is cis heterosexual (Van Der Ros & Motmans, 2015: 163). Over 50% of trans people who participated in the European Union (EU) study claimed that they have experienced discrimination in employment and access to goods and services (FRA, 2020: 20). The same research shows that violence against trans people is

widespread: 47% of trans respondents have reported harassment while 17% experiencing physical or sexual assault (ibid.: 38). There is an increase of concerns over the protection of the rights of trans people within the LGBTIQ movement (Van Der Ros, & Motmans, 2015). This has resulted in an increased visibility of trans people and trans debates in academia, social movements, politics, media, and culture that subsequently backlashed with anti-trans antagonisms from within the feminist movement (Hines, 2019: 145-146).

These antagonisms and tensions can be recognized in form of various feminist discourses over how feminism should conceptualize and respond to trans identities and trans experiences (Pearce et al., 2020). This is not the first time that such tensions occur. Enke (2018) writes that the feminist movement has historically been embedded with both *queerness* and *transness*, but since the 70s, some feminist narratives seek to divide the history of feminism from the history of transness (25-26; 12).

To better understand the animosity of some feminists towards trans people within feminist spaces and to shed a light on the causes for the strong reaction following the appointment of the new director of CWS, we investigated feminist discourses among activists in the post-Yugoslav space. To reach this understanding, we ask:

What effects do the discourses on gender have on feminist movements in the post-Yugoslav space?

To help us answer our research question, we have created two research sub-questions:

- *Which discourses on gender exist within the feminist movement in the post-Yugoslav space?*
- *How do these discourses affect relationships between feminists and feminist organizations?*

This bachelor project aims to fill a knowledge gap by providing an understanding of the effects of various discourses on sex, gender, and trans people in the feminist movements in the post-Yugoslav space. To understand the feminist discourses, we opted for a qualitative research design (Bryman, 2012: 36). This approach aims to bring in-depth knowledge of the real-life experiences, thoughts, and beliefs of feminist activists and their understanding of the issues that emerge over the inclusion/exclusion of trans people in the movement.

2. State of the Art

In this chapter we will introduce relevant knowledge and research on our topic. The relationship between feminist movements and trans people has not been researched in the post-Yugoslav space. However, it has been extensively researched in the UK and the US. Additionally, we found many parallels between the discourses used internationally and the ones used in the post-Yugoslav space. As we live in a globalized world where spatial barriers have mostly disappeared, it is a reasonable assumption that international feminist discourses will affect regional and local discourses as well (Ahmed, 2014: 153; Harvey, 1990: 426).

A Trans History of Feminism

“[...]as long as there have been transgender people and feminist movements, there have been trans people active in them” (Abelson, 2018: 44).

The feminist movement has its origins in the 19th century and is concerned with advancing the economic, political, and social rights of women (Epure, 2014: 514). From a historical perspective, there have been three waves of feminism, each focused on certain aspects, from suffrage to emancipation, discrimination, identity, and wider social change (ibid.). Some recognize a fourth-wave feminism, which is characterized by being facilitated mostly in the online spaces and for putting more focus on everyday concerns of women, such as sexual violence (Parry et al., 2018). There have been at least three different ideological feminist approaches on how to change the position of women in society: liberal, socialist, and radical (Epure, 2014). Liberal feminism aims to change women's position by focusing on a change of legal, political, and social rights to achieve equality with men (ibid. 515). Socialist feminism sees social change through the redistribution of labor and economic or materialist matters used in the subordination of women (ibid.: 516). This includes the abolishment of all hierarchical social structures such as the nuclear family (ibid.). Radical feminism appeared in the 1970s as a critique of mainstream (liberal) feminism and offers a solution for achieving social change (ibid. 517). They claim that women are the most oppressed class that can only be liberated by focusing on women's issues by building new knowledge and practice based on women's own lived experiences (ibid.) This can only be achieved through a separation from men (ibid.: 517-518).

Histories of trans people and the history of feminism are inherently connected (Enke, 2018: 25-26) and are important for the understanding of current dynamics of the trans/feminist debate. Enke (2018: 10) writes that second wave feminism, or the feminism of the 1970s, has for many feminists become symbolic of trans exclusionary feminism. However, second wave feminism was far from uniform (Halberstam, 2018: 116). The subject of trans people within the movement “*was debated, scrutinized, discussed, and accepted and rejected by different feminists at different times*” (Halberstam, 2018: 116). In fact, trans people have always been at the center of feminist movements (Abelson, 2018: 43), including the feminism of the 1970s (Enke, 2018: 11). This is where Enke (2018) introduces the concept of *plausible histories*. They argue that knowledge and memory is produced collectively into a plausible rendition of what happened in the past (9). Any inaccuracies in that rendition can “*tell us critical things about that collectivity*” (Enke, 2018: 9). Enke continues to argue that the plausible history of second wave feminism as being inherently anti-trans could serve the purpose of continuously relegating trans people as newcomers to feminism (ibid.: 11).

According to many scholars, Janice Raymond’s 1979 publication of *The Transsexual Empire: The Making of the She-Male* represented a turning point for second wave feminism (Abelson, 2018: 48; Carrera-Fernández & DePalma, 2020: 749; Halberstam, 2018: 108; Hines, 2019: 146; Hines, 2020: 707; Koyama, 2006: 700; Pearce et al., 2020: 682; Saeidzadeh & Strid, 2020: 314; Whittle, 2006: 195; Williams, 2020: 720). The book gave feminists a framework to see trans people as alien invaders and tools of the patriarchy (Whittle, 2006: 195). In the book, Raymond argues that “*All transsexuals rape women’s bodies by reducing the real female form to an artifact, appropriating this body for themselves [...]*” (Raymond, 1979: 104 in Whittle, 2006: 196). She argues that trans bodies are synthetic, unnatural, and broken where cisgender bodies are natural and whole (Williams, 2020: 720). Raymond later directly affected the US legislation when trans medical care was taken off both private and public insurance coverage in the eighties (Williams, 2020: 727). Whittle (2006) argues that the book had “*far-reaching ideological effects*” (196) as it sanctions the oppression and silencing of trans people within feminist spaces (ibid.: 197).

The large majority of papers we read on this topic agree on one thing: “*[...]as long as there have been transgender people and feminist movements, there have been trans people active in them*” (Abelson, 2018: 44). The anti-trans feminists did indeed cause harm; however, they were actually

a small, albeit loud, group of people (Enke, 2018: 24). Whittle (2006: 194) argues that feminism needs to leave its history of internal conflict behind to move forward together with a new consensus of the rules.

Trans and Anti-Trans Discourses

In 2020, a whole edition of *The Sociological Review Monographs* was published starting with the article *TERF Wars: An Introduction*, the subject of which was to explore debates of trans inclusion “*within (and beyond) feminism*” (Pearce et al., 2020: 690). The following section will use essays from this monograph alongside essays from a 2006 collection of trans research and Ahmed’s 2016 article *An Affinity of Hammers* to take a look at anti-trans discourses in feminist spaces.

Saeidzadeh and Strid (2020) write that the antagonisms against trans people within the feminist movement have revolved around certain contestations, one of them being ‘who and what is a woman’ (312). According to Hines (2020), anti-trans feminists uses the sex/gender binary to construct “*the identity and experience of woman through a purely biological lens*” (713). However, “‘*woman*’ was (and often continues to be) used as shorthand for white, wealthy, non-disabled, cisgender and heterosexual women” (Jones & Slater, 2020: 837). This creates a very narrow definition of womanhood used to police not only the bodies of trans women, but cis and intersex women as well, particularly women of color (ibid.; Carrera-Fernández & DePalma, 2020: 754-544).

Koyama (2006) argues that most rationales used by feminists to exclude trans women are racist (702). She writes that ‘radical feminists’ rank the patriarchy above all other forms of oppressions (ibid.: 701). This allows them to claim that trans women should be excluded for having experienced male privilege at some point in their lives while ignoring white privilege all together, since what matters the most is male oppression (ibid.: 702). Koyama concludes that “*it is never feminist when some women are silenced and sacrificed to make room for the more privileged women*” (ibid.: 703).

Namaste (2006) argues that the inherent gendering of public spaces reinforces heterosexual hegemony (590). However, the toilet is one of the few spaces that are explicitly gender-separated and has thus become a site of conflict between trans exclusive- and trans inclusive feminists (Jones

& Slater, 2020: 834). Women's public bathrooms are simultaneously constructed as a place of refuge from- and a place where women are particularly vulnerable to male violence (ibid.: 838). Feminist campaigns paint trans women as potential sexual predators using politics of fear to argue that they should be excluded from women only spaces like bathrooms (ibid.: 839). Besides trans women, these discourses also affect women that present masculine in any way (ibid.: 844). However, cis people are far more likely to perpetrate violence against trans women than trans women against cis women (Pearce et al., 2020: 681). Pearce et al. (2020) argue that "*this notion of toilet 'safety' is part of a wider protectionist politics around (cis) women's bodies that function to protect idealized notions of white female vulnerability*" (680). Additionally, Jones and Slater (2020) argue that this discourse actively constricts the mobility of trans people since people's ability to go out into the world and even work is directly connected to whether or not they will be able to eventually use a public toilet (842-845).

Pearce et al. (2020) and Ashley (2020) argue that anti-trans feminists strategically mobilize science to present their political views as immutable (689; 779). For example, by using biology to exclude trans- and intersex women from women's sports, "*authorities lay claim to the 'neutrality' and 'objectivity' of science [...] even if it has been contested in social scientific and humanities scholarship for decades*" (Pearce et al., 2020: 689).

According to Ahmed (2016), trans exclusive feminists similarly weaponize free speech. They argue that accusations of transphobia are used to silence them (24). However, Pearce et al. (2020) show how these claims of silence are being broadcasted across mainstream media and political events (685). By claiming that they are being silenced, their "*dominant views become rearticulated as if they are minority views [...]*" (ibid.: 25). Ahmed (2016) concludes that "*[to] give an account of trans people as causing violence (by virtue of being trans) is to cause violence against trans people*" (26).

LGBTIQ and Feminist Movement(s) in the Post-Yugoslav Space

The feminist movement in the post-Yugoslav space dates back from the late 1970s and early 1980s when the first feminist academic societies were founded (Miškovića Kajevska, 2017: 28; 44). Yugoslav lesbian organizations emerged from the feminist movement in late 1980s, when feminist lesbians began to recognize each other in the feminist spaces and started working together

(Mladenović, 2016: v-vi). Soon after, gay men joined the lesbians which created the early foundation for the contemporary LGBTIQ movement in the post-Yugoslav space (Bilić, 2016b: 118-119; Butterfield, 2016: 25-26; Mladenović, 2016: x). This movement gained more visibility and influence after the first Pride Marche was organized in Belgrade and Zagreb at the turn of the century (ibid.). LGBTIQ and feminist movements are characterized by cross-border cooperation and solidarity termed *transnational solidarity networks* (Bilić & Kajinić 2016: 6). This suggests that Bilić and Kajinić (2016) see LGBTIQ and feminist movements in the post-Yugoslav space as a single intersecting movement. Hodžić et al. (2016) further explains that the post-Yugoslav transnational solidarity network is founded on the common political principles of anti-fascism, anti-nationalism, and feminism (37). This intersectional approach opened the space for trans activism, because some lesbian and feminist organizations provided support for trans activism before trans organizations were founded (ibid.: 35).

The literature we found shows that both feminist and LGBTIQ movements in the post-Yugoslav space have experienced several internal tensions and at times even splits. A major split within the feminist movement occurred during the early 1990s around the discourse of victimhood and positions of feminist organizations towards the Yugoslav Wars (Miškovska Kajevska, 2017: 2). The very core of this split was the question of which ethnic group should be considered a perpetrator and which the victim of the war (ibid.). Feminist researcher Miškovska Kajevska (2017) describes this split as “*painful and upsetting*”, and it is still considered to be a “*politically and emotionally laden topic*” today (1). She differentiates the split between ‘*nationalist*’ and ‘*anti-nationalist*’ feminist positions (2-3). The nationalist feminist position clearly identifies perpetrators as members of an ethnic group, whereas the anti-nationalist feminist position identifies all men as the perpetrators, and all women and children as the victims of (sexual) violence, prioritizing gender over ethnicity (ibid.: 5-7). These divisions were less obvious in Serbia compared to Croatia, where the war was fought at the time when the split occurred (ibid.).

Other inter-feminist tensions and antagonisms we found are more directly related to our research problem. Kahlina (2006) writes about her experiences as a student at CWS and emphasized that lesbian authors, lesbian experiences, and lesbian perspectives are systemically marginalized within the scopes of activities of the CWS. It is, however, important to note that she wrote in 2006 and in 2020, modules on both lesbian and queer studies were offered (CWS, 2020).

Closer to our research problem is the book chapter about non-heterosexual feminist women in activism that includes a short reference about the position of trans women in the post-Yugoslav feminist movement (Vuković and Petričević, 2019). There is a story of a trans woman activist who clashed with radical lesbian feminists at a well-known post-Yugoslav lesbian event called Lesbian Sunday over their claims that trans women “*are not women*” and trans men are “*actually lesbians*” (ibid.: 145). The editor of this book considered the position of lesbian activism against trans people an emerging issue (Radoman, 2019: 201). She identifies two positions, the trans-exclusionary radical lesbian feminism and the non-essentialist approach that goes beyond identity politics (ibid.). Radoman (2019) presents these two conflicting discourses through the voice of two activists (201-202): The non-essentialist discourse emphasizes that trans people have always been part of the common struggle, they have just not been accepted as equal and have remained invisible. The exclusionary discourse claims that there is a need for to fight for lesbian separation and a necessity for women-only spaces since “*lesbian activism has been hit by the queer and trans movement*” (ibid.).

Post-war trauma, heterosexism, and reinforced rigid patriarchal gendered and societal norms, xenophobia, and nationalism, as well as the strong influence of organized religions, shape everyday life experiences in the post-Yugoslav space (Hodžić et al, 2016: 36). All this makes lives especially difficult for trans and queer people (Hodžić et al, 2016: 36.) We found further evidence that trans people in Croatia and Serbia experience violence, discrimination, and social exclusion (Zagreb Pride, 2018). Trans people experience systematic discrimination and a lack of recognition of their identity in their everyday lives (ibid.: 6). Violence against trans people in Croatia is prevalent and trans people experience significantly more sexual and psychological violence than cis LGB people (Milković, 2013: 88-89). Trans people in Serbia also experience widespread violence and discrimination, including cyberbullying (ERA, 2019: 30). LGBTIQ organizations warn that trans people are at risk of homelessness and poverty due to widespread discrimination including discrimination in public administration and judiciary system (ibid.). Trans people in Serbia do not report hate crimes to the police; however, the media frequently report about hate crimes against trans women, including the police violence against trans women sex workers (Mršević, 2017: 42-43).

Besides widespread homo- and transphobia, LGBTIQ communities in the post-Yugoslav space also face political organization advocating against their rights. Right-wing groups have been reframing their messages and found new resources for gaining wider public support (Swimelar, 2019; Vučković Juroš et al., 2020). These new ways of organizing include appropriating the tactics and human rights discourses of feminist and LGBTIQ movements such as a organization of a referendum campaign against same sex marriage (ibid.). In Croatia, these right-wing groups have a much wider scope of issues they mobilize against, including LGBTIQ rights and abortion (Vučković Juroš et al., 2020: 1549), while in Serbia they are almost exclusively focused against LGBTIQ people (Swimelar, 2019).

The global and post-Yugoslav trans and feminist discourses differ in their historical contexts and paths. However, maybe surprisingly, current struggles are shared and the anti-trans discourse follows a recognizable matrix: trans people are *othered* and constructed as a threat. The Yugoslav Wars left a strained feminist movement that is still under an immense attack from right wing and patriarchal structures. The widening of feminist themes in the last decades led to a mobilization of a new generation of feminist activists who look at the structural causes of inequalities within the society rather than focus on violence against women predominantly. These were our starting points. However, we recognize many knowledge gaps around our problem area so in the next chapter we present a project design that will help us better understand the current issues.

3. Project Design

3.1. Methodology

To answer our research question, we decided to collect qualitative data because that would provide us nuanced knowledge about real-life experience that we cannot obtain with quantitative approach. With a quantitative research design, it would have been difficult to provide an understanding of such a complex phenomenon like discourse. Therefore, we collected and analyzed non-numerical data by talking directly to feminists in the post-Yugoslav space and by collecting the public statements issued by feminist organizations. We created a combination of inductive and deductive research design (Perry & Jensen, 2001). We first thoroughly studied the literature to develop pre-

categories which we then searched for in our data (ibid.). At the same time, we remained open to new possibilities and dimensions other than our pre-categories and we did not disregard any data we came across (ibid.). We did not work with hypotheses, so there was nothing to ‘prove or reject’. This research is both theory and data driven. This approach proactively engages with the social actors that are participating in this research. However, it is contextual and cannot be generalized to other situations.

Philosophical Foundations

We have taken feminist social constructivism as our philosophical standpoint. This standpoint assumes that reality is constructed through human thoughts, involvements, and interactions (Egholm, 2014: 145). We agree with the social constructivist ontological assumptions that realities are collectively created by different social groups who have their own social interests and goals (ibid.). We believe that social science should aim towards a better society and ultimately the liberation of the oppressed (ibid. 141). As feminists, we are concerned about how social interactions and various understandings of social realities constitute oppression (Friedman, 2006: 182).

The epistemology of feminist social constructivism is relativist (Egholm, 2014: 145). This means that the nature of knowledge is shaped by social contexts and that the dominant social groups get to tell their truth as opposed to non-dominant groups (ibid.). Berger and Luckmann (1992) wrote about *common sense knowledge*, which is a sense of reality that is constructed and repeated in everyday life through interactions between individuals in the social world (36-37). This way the social world influences people through routines and habits that are repeated over time which makes them socially institutionalized (ibid.). This kind of knowledge is implicit and has an almost natural feeling about it because it is seen as self-evident. We are critical of this kind of knowledge, and we want to understand how the process of assigning meaning to phenomena works (Egholm, 2014: 145). While working with our data, we critically and collaboratively reflect on the context in which we and our research participants define our realities (Friedman, 2006: 188).

Processes of meaning-making are conducted by communicating through language and social practices via verbal and nonverbal interactions (Thomsen & Andersen, 2000: 164). This process occurs within the *discourse*, which is an extended sample of either spoken or written language that

shapes the interaction between the speaker and the one addressed in a social context (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 67). Furthermore, discourse is a social practice that produces and changes knowledge, identities, and social relations (ibid.: 65). This gives us an understanding that discourses have a real-life consequence on social actors.

A meaning that is constructed and assigned to phenomena is seen as relative and fluid but also socially motivated (Fairclough, 1992: 74). This means that parts of society or institutions, or in our case, research participants and their organizations have reasons behind their assignments of certain meanings to certain concepts. Our goal was to unravel these reasons by understanding their motivation and their consequences. To do so, we must first understand a difference between a signifier and signified, which are linguistic terms commonly used in social science (Fairclough, 1992: 74-75). A *signifier* represents a sign - or spoken or written word - that we find in our primary or secondary data. The signifier can be assigned with a plurality of various meanings and possible interpretations, called *signifieds*. Through a discursive process called *articulation*, the *signified* is either confirmed or modified (Egholm, 2014: 154). This confirmation or modification represents a real-life and concrete social situation that consequently creates a social space where meanings are shared among certain groups of people in society or institution (ibid.).

To answer our research question, first we had to collect data that presents multiple meanings, realities and discourses described by our research participants. These meanings and realities are discursively negotiated through interpretations of real-life social experiences (Egholm, 2014.: 150). This means that some of our research participants with similar experiences might easily agree about which reality is true while others cannot. Since different social groups have different experiences and different interpretations of their realities, this leads to conflicts over which understanding of reality is the true one. In such conflicts, feminist social constructivism focuses on the role of the sources of social dominance in the construction of social phenomena (Friedman, 2006: 182). The feminist social constructivist assumptions are that *dominant identities* and *dominant discourses*, cause *oppressive practices* and *oppressed identities* (ibid.). Identities and practices are also important for Fairclough who stresses that they are created discursively in the same way as *reality* or *knowledge* (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 90). This means that dominant discourses produce dominant practices and identities.

A discourse that maintains social relations of domination is an *ideology*, according to Fairclough (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 75). This means that maintaining the status quo is in the interest of hegemonic power. Fairclough sees hegemony as a process of reaching a consensus among competing discourses on a common meaning of discursive elements, although he acknowledges that the existence of competing discourses is a potential for resistance (ibid. 76). We see this resistance as a means of competition for the oppressed discourses to transform the power relations. Fairclough offers a solution - social change occurs when elements of discourse are articulated in new ways (ibid.). This assumes a change in the meanings and social realities which are, according to Fairclough, these discursive elements (ibid.). This is done by making people aware of the discourse(s) that reinforce unequal power relations (ibid.: 88).

We agree with the stance that social science should have the ambition to challenge widely accepted assumptions and have an impactful effect on the everyday lives of the people (Egholm, 2014: 144-145). To challenge these assumptions, we need to understand the language and the discourse our research participants use, since this is essential for understanding the reality of our everyday lives (Berger & Luckmann, 1966: 51-52). While doing this research and engaging with our research participants, we were also challenging our preconceptions by continuously reflecting on our social positions (ibid.: 23). Therefore, in the next section, we presented our positionalities.

Project Team Positionalities

We took a partial insider-outsider positionality in this research (Flick, 2009: 111-112; Miškovska-Kajevska, 2017: 10; Rowe, 2014: 628). This means that one of the research team members belongs to a group that we study (full insider-outsider perspective), while the other takes more of an outsider perspective. We approached this research by reflecting on our own positions in the research. Starting from a feminist social constructivists position, we considered ourselves as an integral part of the social world we investigated both as researchers and as feminists. As such, our beliefs have affected and influenced the way we understand our research participants and how we construct their realities. We agree with Haraway (1988) that our preconceptions cannot be ignored in this research so instead we offer our full perspective to the readers and integrate our positionalities in this research project (581). We make our positionalities visible in Annex 1 to make our unconscious bias explicit.

Our positionalities, particularly one researcher's position as an insider-outsider and the other's as a woman, provided us with access to the activists we are researching, and it meant we had a certain amount of trust from our research participants before we even started the interviews. Aside from one, all our research participants seemed comfortable sharing their views and experiences with us, despite the fact that the topic is sensitive. Our backgrounds within feminist activism and theory allowed us to understand their processes as well as relate some of their experiences, which garnered an amicable atmosphere at the interviews and furthered our overall understanding of our data.

To minimize the negative effects of the power we embody and to make our privileges clear in the research process, we continuously reflected, collectively or individually, on our positionalities, which included our past experiences, beliefs, and other factors that can influence the research process (Vanner, 2015: 2-4). Our research participants often pushed us in unexpected or surprising directions in conversation, which we curiously explored, as this challenged our preconceptions, bringing new knowledge. These reflections were made by making ourselves 'visible' in this research, which means that in the following sections of this chapter, we rigorously explain each segment of the research design. Furthermore, we use a triangulation strategy to improve the quality of our data and later discussion (Flick, 2009: 405). This means that in addition to exposing our positions within this project and directly gathering data from research participants, we also introduce the secondary data and the outsiders' perspective. The outsiders' perspective represents the theoretical and empirical contribution of other authors we found in the literature which can challenge our preconceptions about the problem area (Chapters 2 & 4). This way we achieve a "balance of biases" which enhances the 'internal validity of data (Jones, 2001).

Methods

In the following sections, we present our methods of data collection. We have collected two different sets of data to understand the discourses around trans people in the feminist movement. Here we also present our recruiting strategies and describe our sample.

Our second set of data is textual data, or public statements from feminist organizations which we gathered from their websites or social media from December 2020 when CWS appointed their new director.

Semi-Standardized Interviews; Sampling and Recruiting

Following guidelines from Flick (2009: 156-158), we conducted a semi-standardized interview guide (IG) (Annex 2). The IG contained 13 open-ended questions on various topics we found important for answering our research questions. These included the research participants' relationship with feminism, their understanding of feminist movement's goals in the post-Yugoslav space, various relationships within the movement, as well as their opinion on the current debate on gender, women-only spaces, and womanhood in general. The semi-structured interview format with open-ended questions allowed us to avoid strictly following our IG, giving the research participants more space to share their subjective and personal experiences or thoughts (Flick, 2009: 156). This includes thoughts and opinions that are explicit and which interview participants can express in detail in answering open questions. Inspired by the research design of Miškovska Kajevska (2017: 14-15), we also offered our research participants to raise one custom-made question for themselves and/or for other research participants. By doing so, we wanted to gather richer data and give more control over the research process to our research participants. This way our research participants could have raised issues they believe are important for the feminist movement in the post-Yugoslav space. However, none of the 12 research participants created and raised a self-designed question (Annex 2, question #13). We gave all research participants the open-ended questions in advance. We chose to do so to ensure that the consent of our research participants was informed and to build trust with those feminists who were skeptical of our intentions, but also to allow them more time to consider which questions they were and were not comfortable discussing. At the interviews, however, we spontaneously asked them numerous follow-up and probing questions (Flick, 2009: 171). Some more general follow-up questions were prepared in advance but, in most cases, we made them up on the spot. This gave us the flexibility to place more focus on certain topics during the interview. This was important when a research participant had more to say about one aspect of our research interests compared to others that were not so familiar to them.

Our sampling method was purposive (Flick, 2009: 122). We chose this method to recruit research participants who are social actors directly involved or affected by the feminist discourse on gender and trans people. The advantage of this method is that it allows us to recruit people with experience and knowledge that could help us answer the research questions. The limitations are that we gain

only knowledge from certain social actors. Our research misses input from all the affected social actors, in particular from those belonging to the vulnerable part of the society most affected by this discourse, such as trans women migrants and sex workers. We also did not approach feminists and organizations who remain publicly silent about this issue. Since LGBTIQ and feminist movements are interconnected and they consider themselves as part of the same movement in the post-Yugoslav space, we have approached activists who identify as *feminists* and are associated with the organizations that are *feminist*. At the beginning of the research process, we have identified which feminist organizations were critical to CWS's appointment of the new director, and which organizations signed a letter of support to CWS and the new director. From the insider-outsider's position of the project team member, we mapped feminists associated or working with the most recognizable organizations from either side of the conflict and reached out to 15 potential research participants directly via email or social media. These 15 feminist activists are affiliated or have been affiliated with the following organizations: *B.a.B.e.*, *Center for Civil Courage*, *CWS*, *Faktiv*, *FemRevolt*, *Geten LGBTIQ*, *Labris*, *Women in Black*, *Trans Aid*, *K-zona*, *XY Spectrum*, and *Zagreb Pride*. All but 2 replied and agreed to participate in this research. After initially agreeing, one research participant asked not to be interviewed, stating that the discussion would be too emotionally taxing for her.

In total, 12 research participants have been recruited and they represent our research sample. Our sample is diverse in terms of age, gender, sexuality, social class, and nationality as well as how they have positioned themselves in the conflict around CWS and the discourse on gender in general. Six feminists are based in Croatia, and five in Serbia. Their age ranges from the mid-20s to mid-60s. Three research participants identify as trans - one trans woman and two trans men. Two feminists identify as lesbian, while one identifies as a queer woman and five as straight women. Three out of 12 have publicly sided with CWS, including one who is one of the founders of CWS. One has shown sympathies to CWS on social media, while another one is a member organization that is currently split over the support of either side. Five research participants were undoubtedly critical to appointment of the new director and openly advocate the trans-inclusive feminist approach. All live in their country's capitals, Belgrade and Zagreb. Our sample differs in socio-economic status; from unemployed, retired, contract-workers to full-time employed workers. They also have diverse educational backgrounds ranging from high school level education to PhD degrees.

The interviews were conducted and recorded online via Zoom, Jitsi or Skype in synchronous form (Flick, 2009: 266). This means that we asked interview participants the questions directly, as we would do during the face-to-face interviews. Each interview lasted approximately one hour and all of them were audio recorded. In the recruitment letter (Annex 3) research participants were also offered to speak to the female researcher alone, and it was implied that one research participant favored this option. When both research project team members were present, we exchanged the roles of the main interviewer and supporting interview. We also documented non-verbal data. The interviews were conducted in English, but research participants were informed that they could freely express some of their thoughts in their native language if they had trouble expressing them in English. All the Serbo-Croatian translations and language-specific references have been addressed by a project team member who is a native Serbo-Croatian speaker in the form of notes that have been incorporated in the interview transcripts.

Secondary Data: Statements of Feminist Organizations

To support our findings, in addition to qualitative interview data we collected and selected secondary data from online sources. These are written articles from websites and publicly available social media content created by feminist activists and organizations. In total, we found 36 relevant pieces of written data which we screenshot and stored. The collected data contains interviews with feminist activists published on relevant feminist websites, statements of feminist organizations, individual social media posts, press releases, blogs, and other written content. Our collection does not include video content, visual data, social media content that is not from Facebook, as well as social media content that represents a direct engagement of individuals to the content posted on Facebook (e.g., comments, shares, and other reactions). Our criteria for collecting and selecting the textual data were credibility, representativeness, and a clear meaning or intent of the statement (Flick, 2009: 257-258). We collected data from authentic sources, websites, and social media that are managed by credible publishers, public or non-profit media or feminist organizations.

Since we have recruited a diverse sample, including some of the authors of the online content, we have decided to select only the written statements of feminist organizations for the analysis. This way, we were able to ask our research participants more about the online content on gender and trans people, and about the positions of feminist organizations that they may or may not disagree

with. In total, we have selected 13 statements from the period between December 8 and December 24, 2020. Two of the statements are support letters. Each contains over 150 endorsements of individuals or other organizations.

These statements represent a *documentary reality* with a distinct purpose in mind at the time of their creation (Bryman, 2012: 555). The particular purpose of these statements was to represent the collective political positions of larger groups of feminist activists regarding their understanding of gender and their thoughts on the participation of trans people in the feminist movement. Furthermore, we have selected only immediate reactions of feminist organizations and counter-reactions to the appointment of the new director of CWS, because during the selection process, we estimated that this content addresses directly our research problem. The content we excluded from further analysis contained historical or theoretical discussions on the relationship between the feminist and LGBTIQ moment in the local context, translations from various English language sources, or blogs and interviews with feminists we recruited for this research project. We decided to discuss the issues with the research participants directly.

Data Analytical Strategy

Merely analyzing the text that we gathered is insufficient in gathering a constructivist understanding of the creation of post-Yugoslav feminist realities. To understand how our research participants make sense of the social world, we turned to Fairclough and his approach to data analysis called critical discourse analysis (CDA). This way allows us to identify links between our textual data, meaning, and societal and cultural processes and structures (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 66). CDA offers an analytical framework for empirical research on communication and society which enabled us to analyze texts, or in our case, the two transcriptions data in three dimensions: i) *textual*; ii) *discursive practices*, and iii) *social practices* (ibid.: 68-69).

Applied to our project, the first dimension of discourse was our data - the words our research participants used when they answered our questions, or the statements the feminist organizations have produced to position themselves around the appointment of the new director of CWS. The relationship between texts and social practice is mediated by the second dimension, *discursive practices* (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 69). Discursive practices are values and attitudes to which our research participants and their organizations assign different phenomena. For Fairclough

(1992), various discourses which are struggling with each other for hegemony are articulated within ‘orders of discourse’ which he defines as a “*totality of discursive practices within an institution or society, and the relationships between*” (43). This means that within the post-Yugoslav feminist orders of discourse represented in our sample, we will first identify which are articulated and then describe a relationship between them. The last dimension, the social practices are the societal effects of discourse, such as social relations, identities, norms, or rules that we are interested in discovering. Societal practices reproduce and change knowledge, identities, and social relations including power relations (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 65). The societal practices in our case do not apply to the society of the post-Yugoslav space as a whole but to the society of the feminists and organizations they affiliate themselves with.

In the following paragraphs we describe how the data was prepared and processed for discourse analysis. We have transcribed and recorded interviews and systemized secondary data as if we were doing a regular content analysis. However, in the Findings (Chapter 5), we present them within the CDA framework.

The collected audio data was transcribed with the help of the online software Otter.ai. The software-produced transcriptions were first double-checked for clarity and accuracy. Then both researchers entered their notes and markups into the text to indicate non-verbal feedback, speakers’ non-verbal noises, pauses, emphasis, unintelligible speech, anonymization, translations, and additional notes. The primary data transcript (Tr.1) is a 212-page and 6052-lines document containing transcription and notes from 12 interviews. We use line numbers to reference the data from Tr. 1 in the Findings and *Discussion* chapters (e.g., Tr.1: *line number*). The transcription is not annexed to this submission. There are more details on what Tr.1 contains and how the supervisor or exam censor can request it written in Annex 4.

Our secondary data is prepared and ordered in a similar process. We have collected, sorted, and arranged all the statements in the original language (Serbo-Croatian and English) into a single 24-page 709-lines document containing 13 statements from feminist organizations. In the Findings and Discussion chapters, we reference the secondary data as Transcript 2 (e.g., Tr.2: *line number*). The transcription of secondary data with links to the original sources is annexed to this submission as Annex 5.

Once the transcripts were finalized, we started the thematic coding process (Flick, 2009: 318-319). Texts were coded by using the online software Dedoose (V. 8.3.47b). Coding is a process of categorizing and labeling verbal data by assigning different concepts or themes to texts. (ibid.: 307). We assigned codes based on the combination of a pre-set list of codes that emerged from the literature and theory as well as codes developed throughout the coding process (Thomas, 2006: 238). Hence, our approach was a combination of deductive and inductive coding. The codes were then categorized into a broader collection of codes (Thomas, 2006: 241-242). In total, we assigned more than 33 different codes which we then organized into 6 parent codes. We arranged these parent codes in 3 themes: i) *opinions*, ii) *emotions*, iii) *mobilization*. Full list of codes can be found in Annex 6. The codes that were developed throughout the coding process are written in uppercase, while other codes are in lowercase.

3.2. Ethical Considerations

We uphold the principles of honesty, transparency, and accountability detailed in the Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (MHES, 2014: 6) throughout this research process. In addition, we apply feminist ethics by prioritizing respect, dignity, care, and responsibility for our research participants before the outcomes of this research (Edwards & Mauthner, 2012:19).

We asked our research participants for both written and verbal consent before recording their interviews, and they were informed that they could refuse to answer specific questions as well as withdraw from the research at any time. Hence, we offered them full autonomy and control over the research process, in line with feminist ethics. The recordings and anonymized transcription are stored safely and will only be seen upon request by our supervisor and examiner. Therefore, the interview transcripts are not attached to this project. The anonymizations include the names of our research participants who have been assigned other random pseudonyms, and the names of other people our research participants refer to when expressing their disagreement or resentment, whose names are completely removed. All recordings will be deleted after the exam in June 2021 (MHES, 2014: 9).

Our research participants are all part of a relatively small community of feminist activists. It would not be unreasonable to assume that they all know (of) each other. We have therefore taken extra

care to ensure their anonymity, and none were informed who else participated in this research. We have chosen to exclude information that could have been relevant for our analysis if this could lead to disclosing anyone's identity. We are also deliberately vague about who said what in some places to avoid the possibility of people piecing together our research participant's identities. We did this since we cannot predict what will cause further harm and tensions and what will not.

All of these measures are undertaken so that our research participants feel as safe as possible in sharing their thoughts with us. These conditions are all introduced to the research participants before and during the interviews, through the recruitment letter and consent form (Annex 3 & 7).

3.3. (De)limitations

Considering the limited time allocated for this research, we decided to limit ourselves to Serbia and Croatia, even though the post-Yugoslav space encompasses Slovenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro, Macedonia, and Kosovo as well. Hence, when we write 'post-Yugoslav space', we are referring only to Serbia and Croatia. This delimitation pertains to the literature review and the sample. For the same reason, we only reached out to activists from explicitly feminist organizations. This means that we have excluded Marxist activists who also participate in these discussions and have been referred to by some of our research participants. We acknowledge that their discursive practices could be important for understanding anti-trans positions some organizations and activists have taken.

All but one interview was conducted entirely in English, a language that is not native to our research participants. This means that some nuances and meanings were lost in translation. The researcher who speaks Serbo-Croatian was however able to catch some of this data anyways. In addition, we offered the research participants the option of using Serbo-Croatian words to express thoughts in their native language, which most of them did. If we had more time for this research, we could have conducted all the interviews in Serbo-Croatian and then translated them to English for richer data. We believe we have balanced this limitation by introducing the secondary data, which was mostly in Serbo-Croatian. There, we see how activists use words, expressions, and idioms loaded with powerful and sharp meanings which are present in the findings chapter.

Conducting the interviews online came with certain limitations. The video calls limited our opportunity to interpret non-verbal data such as body language (Flick, 2009: 269). This would have helped us to further contextualize our findings and understand which topics are more important to our research participants than others.

4. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

4.1. Theoretical Framework

Affect Theory (Ahmed)

In this section, we examine Sara Ahmed's affect theory, particularly her concepts of *fear*, *vulnerability*, and *discomfort*. According to Bissenbakker and Nebeling (2020), Ahmed's affect theory provides an understanding of how feelings connect subjects and social structures with each other, giving us an opportunity to analyze historical and contemporary contexts without distinguishing between the natural and cultural, and the bodily and social (14). Bissenbakker and Nebeling argue that Ahmed writes in extension of queer feminist theory with inspirations from Judith Butler's theory of performativity (ibid.). Affect theory takes an intersectional starting point, meaning that, when discussing how relations of power work, human bodies and their experiences should be analyzed and observed through multiple socially constructed categories (Ahmed, 2017: 5). Bissenbakker and Nebeling (2020) write that Ahmed uses the term body to show that bodies experience feelings, while discourses determine how we interpret and act on those feelings (14). Thus, emotions must be understood as both bodily and discursive (ibid.). We have aimed to analyze the emotional testimonies of our research participants in such an intersectional approach.

According to Ahmed (2014), *fear* is an emotion that constrains the mobility of certain bodies while enabling others (69). By making a distinction between those that are under threat and those who threaten, the language of fear works to align bodies with or against each other (ibid.: 72). Fear can also be produced by institutionalized social structures such as governments or other institutions to create us/them divides (ibid. 73-76). This fear is discursively and intentionally assigned to bodies that 'could be' a threat (ibid.). Although Ahmed (2014) writes about the way post-9/11 USA assigned fear to the bodies of Arabs and Muslims, we found some similarities with the process of

how fear has been assigned to trans bodies. Ahmed (2014) concludes that fear, and other emotions, experiences, and interactions are framed by past histories of association, which allows certain bodies to be constructed as threatening (63). Fear therefore justifies violence against bodies that are seen as threatening (ibid. 64.).

Fear can also be linked with *home*. Ahmed (2014) argues that fear mobilizes some bodies to occupy more space through an identification with the collective body and *home* (74). She suggests that when people are afraid, they sometimes turn to something known to feel safe, a figurative 'home' (ibid.). Home comes to represent certain values constructed as necessary to survival, and bodies are then aligned either with *home* or with that which threatens *home* (ibid.). This leads to the defense of "*particular social forms or institutions*" (ibid.: 78), which then sustains a normative culture in which we differentiate between legitimate and illegitimate ways of living and conflate the 'legitimate' with survival (ibid.: 149). Ahmed's conceptualization of *home* and *fear* can help us understand why feminists in the post-Yugoslav space have taken a stand to defend or attach particular feminist spaces or institutions.

Ahmed understands *vulnerability* as the *openness* of certain bodies to potential danger (2014: 69). She builds on feminist theories that have argued that narratives of *female vulnerability* regulate women's access to public spaces, rejecting the notion that vulnerability is an inherent characteristic of women's bodies (2017: 69- 70). Here we see that fear constructs some bodies as fearsome or *threatening* while others as afraid or *vulnerable*. This enables some bodies to 'police' or restrict the mobility of others (Ahmed, 2014: 70). Ahmed calls this *the politics of mobility* (ibid.).

Discomfort and its counterpart *comfort* are linked with social privileges. Ahmed writes that "*normativity is comfortable for those who can inhabit it*" (Ahmed, 2014: 147). She describes comfort as when a body is at ease with the environment so much that this privilege can be taken even when one finds themselves in a different environment (ibid.: 148). She gives the example of heterosexuality as a comfort that some bodies inhabit. The same norms that make someone uncomfortable, can make those bodies not able to conform - *uncomfortable* (ibid.). Ahmed argues that the comfort of some bodies is sustained through the invisible labor of others, e.g., when queer couples avoid public displays of affection to not infringe on the 'heterosexuality' of public spaces

(ibid.: 148-149). That same discomfort, however, can open up possibilities to new ways of creating spaces (ibid.: 154).

In her works, Ahmed usually engages with the other feminist theories by taking a critical or affirmative stand. She usually connects feminist theories to everyday life. In *Living a Feminist Life*, Ahmed (2017) writes about a particular painful moment in feminist life that is characterized by collective engagements in breaking the bonds that are damaging (167). She calls this moment a *feminist snap* (ibid.). This happens when a feminist is unwilling to meet the conditions or expectations of others or a revolt against a norm and in a process breaks under pressure (ibid.: 189; 210). We see this as a sort of a realization that ‘enough is enough’. Ahmed argues that having patience is a form of suffering or a capacity to tolerate a delay of a change that a feminist demand (ibid.: 208). Hence, the experience of snap can also be transformative because of other possibilities that can emerge after a bond has been broken (209). This concept can help us discuss the experiences and subjective reasons why some of our research participants decided to split the movement and what emerged from this afterward.

4.2. Conceptual Framework

In this section, we present two concepts that we find useful for discussing our data. The first concept is gender (anti)essentialism, which theorizes on different standpoints on sex and gender that can be seen within feminism and our data. The second concept offers us a cross-generational aspect in analyzing social movements.

Gender Essentialism

Essentialism generally refers to a way of categorizing objects via claims of their true nature (Heyes, 2000: 18). The debate about how to authentically present womanhood while still being able to define its subject has a long history among feminists (Mikkola, 2017: 168). Building on Heyes (2000), Mikkola (2017) defines two categories of gender essentialism, biological and classificatory, and their anti-essentialist critique.

Biological essentialism is the idea that some intrinsic, biological factors determine your sex as well as your traits and abilities (Mikkola, 2017: 169). Such a view invokes a conception of women as

nurturing and passive and of men as eager and passionate (ibid.). Biological essentialism has historically been used to oppress women (ibid.). Feminist scholars like Simone de Beauvoir have countered this position by arguing that women's experiences of discrimination shape them so profoundly that it appears to be a fact of nature (ibid.), thus arriving at the conclusion that gender is a social construction.

Classificatory essentialism is the idea that certain experiences are shared between all women (Mikkola, 2017: 170). However, many feminists have argued that no such common experience exists, so when people have attempted to describe the experience of womanhood, it was mostly the experiences of "*white, middle class, heterosexual, Christian and able-bodies*" women (ibid.: 171). Classificatory anti-essentialists take the stand that women's experiences are culturally specific (ibid.).

Cross-Generational Tensions

Italian sociologist Donatella Della Porta (2009) defines social movements as ways of collectively organizing people who present demands to decision-makers using unconventional political means (1-3). These means could be protests, campaigns, strikes and other influences on public discourse (ibid). Activists mobilize to gain support from the general public and the elites by using all available resources in their environment, most importantly paid or volunteer work (ibid.). This indicates that personal dynamics and relationships in the movement could affect its impact. Della Porta (2019a) argues that in times of severe social and political crisis a significant number of young people engage in collective initiatives (1408).

Building on Della Porta (2019a), Chironi (2019) argues that recently gender movements in Italy have been among the largest and most active ones in mobilizing underprivileged people. This happened because the 2008 economic crisis has hit the disadvantaged people in particular (1470). The increased mobilization of young people in social movements resulted in the creation of new approaches to activism including supporting ideas for achieving a more egalitarian, just, and inclusive society (Della Porta, 2019a: 1408). The new approaches to activism include understanding of horizontal and non-hierarchical forms of organization in both virtual and physical spaces (ibid.). The new ideas include embracing intersectional feminism and queer theory (1420). In addition to this, the new generations of mobilized youth tend to have a more antagonistic attitude

toward the State as well as towards their predecessors in the movement (ibid.). Empowered by increased mobilization, younger activists - women and queer people in particular - engage in more or less open conflicts over the resources, priorities and theoretical inspirations with the activists who have been leading the movements before (Chironi, 2019: 1481). Della Porta calls these conflicts *cross-generational tensions* (Della Porta, 2019b: 1579). In a study of social movements, she suggests giving more attention to generations and how successful they are in mediating their differences (ibid.: 1582). She argues that historical changes and circumstances strongly affect specific age demographics with long-lasting effects in terms of norms, values, and life paths (ibid.: 1582). We can use the concept of cross-generational tensions to discuss how feminists themselves understand the changes that occurred in the post-Yugoslav feminist movement over time and to evaluate possible generational aspects of the inter-feminist tensions in post-Yugoslav feminist space.

5. Findings

In this section we present the findings of our primary and secondary data. The findings are arranged into three themes emerging from the data: i) emotions iii) opinions and iii) mobilization.

Anger, Betrayal and Shock: Competing Discourses and a Feminist Split

We have identified three discourses in the post-Yugoslav feminist movement: *radical*, *moderate*, and *intersectional* feminist discourses. We use these particular terms because our research participants used them to describe themselves. Most of the research participants used the additional designation to indicate the kind of feminism they identify with. Six positioned themselves as queer-feminist, Marxist-feminist, or intersectional-feminist. Since all six share many similar discursive practices we will refer to their discourse as *intersectional* for simplicity. One research participant calls herself a ‘non-radical feminist’ (Tr.1: 2017) to differentiate herself from her radical feminist colleagues. We call this discourse *moderate feminist*. Two other research participants have not used any additional label to feminist. However, they share many similar discursive practices with the moderate feminist participant, so we found the term moderate feminist discourse to be the best fitting for them as well. The remaining two research participants identify as radical feminists, hence *radical feminist discourse*.

We have identified that the split within the post-Yugoslav feminist movement occurred over the issue of recognizing trans people as a part of the feminist struggle and their presence in feminist spaces. Most of the research participants who practice intersectional feminist discourse stressed that the appointment of the new director of CWS represented the breaking point within the ongoing latent conflict that exists between intersectional feminists on one side and radical and moderate feminists on the other.

Eva: *“I thought maybe if I sit down and talk with some of my colleagues, people that I know that are becoming transphobic [that] maybe I can change something. Maybe I can give them articles, maybe we can like, discuss. And there has been a lot of energy spent before everything happened. But unfortunately, little has been changed.”* (Tr.1: 489-492)

Two research participants from Croatia, one radical and one moderate, see the split as an interpersonal conflict and denied that there is a political disagreement in the background.

Dora: *“I really don't have a clear explanation except [...] it is about jealousy. Because the person who is now executive director was a very good friend of the person who accused her of being transphobic. She achieved obviously in the eyes of the other person more.”* (Tr.1: 2627-2631)

This split is perceptible at three levels. The first level is a split between feminist organizations in the movement. Feminist groups that used to collaborate closely have terminated their partnerships. About half of them agree that this has weakened the movement. The second level is a split within feminist organizations which is evident by growing frustration among the members. Examples of such dynamics can be seen within the organizations CWS (Zagreb, Croatia), and lesbian organization Labris (Belgrade, Serbia). The third level is a split in individual relationships. One research participant used words such as ‘sisterhood’ to emphasize the broken bonds among feminists who have closely collaborated in the past. Nearly all research participants told us that the split affected their friendships and professional relationships.

Svetlana: *“I haven't talked to her since. And I'm sure that some ghosting is happening. And another friend as well who is the director of [a feminist festival]. I haven't spoken to*

her since... But it's not that I don't want to talk to her... I think that she doesn't want to talk to me for some reason.” (Tr.1: 1877-1880)

The split has caused a great emotional burden to the research participants. Nearly all of them used words such as *disappointment*, *anger*, and *shock* to describe the split when discussing any of the levels of the split. The intersectional feminists emphasized the feeling of betrayal by the moderate feminists who are, at best, seen as allies to radical feminists. Two moderate feminists have expressed a shock at the turn of events, while the third one, who is about 20 years younger, has expressed more understanding for the intersectional feminists (Tr.1: 2033-2035). The radical feminists emphasized a fear caused by a changing world which is challenging some of their core values.

Mira: *“I’m very much affected [...]by the fact that our comrades are erasing women. It's really...I mean, they're not using that word anymore.” (Tr.1: 3144-3145)*

All research participants were aware of the recent appointment of the director of CWS. Two refused to share their view about the appointment, one intersectional and one radical feminist. We assume that both did so to avoid further escalation of the conflict. Our secondary data show that most organizations that have accused CWS of transphobia for the contentious appointment of the new director had a positive view of CWS’ legacy until this point.

Lesbian organization LORI [In Serbo-Croatian]: *“Exclusion is like a cut made to separate something from yourself but sooner or later you realize you’ve cut off a part of yourself. The Center for Women's Studies were our allies, colleagues, comrades, and we least expected them to take a position of those who would exclude all of us who are not cis and reject all personal, social, and political experiences.” (Tr.2: 227-231)*

Furthermore, nearly all intersectional and moderate feminists had a rather positive attitude on the legacy and the role of radical feminists during the 1990s. In particular, their role in the initiation of actions that led the contemporary LGBTIQ movement in the post-Yugoslav space is considered positive. However, one of the radical feminists insisted that the ‘gay and lesbian movement’ in the post-Yugoslav space was founded without trans people and that the founders should not be called LGBT activists but LB activists instead (Tr.1: 3158-3161).

Divisions and Discourses

We established that the three feminist discourses do not agree around the meanings of three signifiers: *feminism*, *womanhood*, *sex work*, and *safe space*.

For radical feminists, *feminism* is seen as a struggle for the liberation of women against male oppression and all other oppressions are based on the oppression and exploitation of women. During our conversation with radical feminists, we rarely touched on other forms of oppression. The only other intersections they mentioned were *migrant* and *Romani* women. The moderate feminists described feminism as a struggle for equality of genders. They see feminism as a broad base with different currents and approaches that struggle for the ultimate goal, therefore they insisted on feminist unity and a democratic debate where all differences of opinions should be voiced and respected.

Dora: *“I’m aware that there are some women who consider themselves as feminists who have certain concerns about defining a person with the male reproductive organ, a woman.”*

Interviewer: *“Would you also consider them feminists?”* [...]

Dora: *“Well, yeah, definitely, I would say that this is a debate for feminists. And recently one debate was open on that issue, which I think went on the wrong track, because it was more hate speech than civilized debate.”* (Tr.1: 2454-2460)

Intersectional feminists stressed that the goal of a feminist struggle should be the liberation of all people from any kind of oppression and exploitation. Nearly all of them stressed the importance of focusing a feminist struggle on the most marginalized parts of society first.

Eva: *“[F]eminist movement is a movement that should be dedicated to liberation, it should be dedicated to this collective solidarity. So, I cannot see feminism without trans women, without immigrant women, without Romani women.”* (Tr.1: 128-131)

Radical feminists articulated their understanding of *womanhood* through a gender essentialist framework. Although one of them refused to answer a direct question on what constitutes a

woman, her other answers indicated that her standpoint is essentialist since she emphasized bodily experiences as one of the main indicators that differentiate women from others as well as how women share a process of socialization which forms them. While she did not explicitly say that trans women are not women, she most often referred to trans people as ‘trans’, avoiding indications of gender. The other radical feminist defined a woman as an “*adult human female*” (Tr.1: 259). She also did not directly say that trans women are not women. For the three moderate feminists, being a woman is a matter of self-identification. Some used terms such as vulnerable to articulate what it means to be a woman, which corresponds to radical feminist discursive practice.

Vesna: *“I’m a woman. [...] I feel the world from this position. And I know what is to be vulnerable, to be sensitive, to be with and to have less power in a society. To be a woman it means to have more sensitivity, vulnerability and to be physically less strong [than men]. We’re basically born that way. That’s my experience. But because of this, I have a wish to act for a change in the world around me, but also to understand it as well.”* (Tr.1: 2071-2076)

Intersectional feminists offered the most comprehensive answers when talking about womanhood. They first presented their anti-essentialist position by engaging with radical feminist discourse before offering their own answers. Their discursive practices went along the line that there is not a single definition or one universal experience of womanhood.

Eva: *“I would not say that there is ANYTHING that is inherent to certain bodies that make them women, men, or trans. Each person has a different story because of course, we all have different processes that are happening inside of our bodies, different thoughts and these thoughts and these processes interact with these societal parts. So in this interaction different things are formed.”* (Tr.1: 272-275)

Surprisingly, most of the research participants discussed sex work unprompted. We found that the three discursive practices around sex work somewhat corresponded with their position towards trans people. About half of the research participants emphasized *sex work* as a divisive issue in the feminist movement. Radical feminists were staunchly against what they call a ‘state’ of women being “*in prostitution*” (Tr.1: 2822). They emphasized that the goal of feminism is to stop the

sexual exploitation of women, including those women who are ‘in prostitution’. Hence, ‘prostitution’ should be criminalized.

Lana: *“I think that biological man and capitalism have [an] interest in exploitation of female reproductive capacities, and female bodies, in [a] sexual way. Like most of the men are attracted to women and that's the reason why women can be exploited in sex industry. Of course, not only women are exploited in sex industry, but women are much more exploited than other demographics.”* (Tr.1: 3337-3341)

Two moderate feminists called on a broad feminist debate around sex work which they refer to by both the terms - ‘sex work’ and ‘prostitution’. One of them insisted that sex workers voices should be centered in this debate (Tr.1: 4708-4715). Similar articulation of sex work is offered by intersectional feminists, although they never referred to sex work as ‘prostitution’.

The meanings our research participants constructed for *feminism* and *woman(hood)* determined their discursive practices about *safe spaces*. The spaces they referred to were workshops, spaces of their own organizations, March 8 celebrations, public bathrooms, and safe houses for women victims of partner violence. Radical feminists view safe spaces as woman-only spaces, where ‘a woman’ is articulated through a gender essentialist standpoint. Hence, trans women are not allowed into women-only spaces. They emphasized, however, that other groups should organize and define their safe spaces however they want, as long as radical feminists are not forced to open their spaces to those they do not consider to be women.

Mira: *“[F]or example, a man who transitions into [a] woman; they don't understand women. Really! I mean, they DO understand MORE [than cis men] because they see in their real life that they are treated differently than when they were seen outside as men. Because there is obvious oppression, discrimination, but really, they don't understand the history of experience of all these different kinds of fears that the girls have.”* (Tr.1: 3094-3098)

Moderate feminists approached this issue depending on the context or said that this decision is for feminist groups themselves to make.

Ivana: *I think that there are situations from time to time where women should be alone and discuss these issues on this readiness to subordination; being used to not being the one who are vocal and express opinions, and things like that. Because still it's male dominated society.” (Tr.1: 4912-4914]*

Intersectional feminists agreed that women-only spaces were needed in the past or are still needed when working with some specific groups of women such as Romani women, women refugees, and asylum seekers. However, this should be an exception. They argued that the feminists in post-Yugoslav space should instead create safe feminist spaces for all.

Lea: *“Behind those safe spaces, their main premise is that we are something different. Women are something different, their experiences, their sensations, their lives are different than the other sex. So it's just rooted in that quite firm binarism. [...] So it is deeply wrong. That's why we have the mainstream understanding that feminism is something only for girls and women and not for men. And that also produces all kinds of prejudice in the dominant narratives [...]” (Tr.1: 4386-4392)*

Feminist Mobilizations

Nearly all our research participants stated that they joined the feminist movement because of an external social, economic, or political crisis. They mentioned the 90s Yugoslav Wars, 2009 student protests, or the 2013 referendum on banning same-sex marriage in Croatia. Since the split, we identified a new feminist mobilization. Both radical and intersectional feminists mobilized for wider support immediately after the conflict escalated publicly. Radical activists engaged in the work of CWS and intend to found new radical feminist organizations. The intersectional feminists called for the creation of a new intersectional feminist movement.

Trans Aid [in Serbo-Croatian]: *“Despite the increase in transphobia in places we considered our own until yesterday, we are becoming more aware of the voices of our friends who refuse to accept such appropriations, and with whom we continue to work to link all our efforts to break down all forms of oppression in every corner of our space. Emancipation is possible only through collective and integrative feminist, Marxist, queer organization and action” (Tr.2: 306-310)*

The three trans research participants have all offered different strategies for mobilization. One of them engages in online discussions and production of online content which has backfired with online abuse (Tr.1: 1292-1347). One has taken a strategy of not publicly confronting radical feminists, arguing that this would negatively affect the wellbeing of trans youth (Tr.1: 4050-4053). The third trans activists emphasized that what has been said or written lacks trans perspectives.

Luka: *“I think that it is important that a feminist media opens a space to trans people and moves beyond a theoretical discussion where one feminist approach fights with another. If trans people could express themselves, it would show a real statement to TERFs - what matters is real life, and not their theoretical debate.”* (Tr.1: 3629-3632)

Moderate feminists do not seem to be mobilizing. They insist that feminists should focus on collaboration around issues they can all agree on. According to our findings, these are economic, domestic, and sexual violence against women. It seems that moderate feminists are trying to avoid contributing to the further divide. For example, some events, such as Lesbian Week, a festival organized in different locations across the post-Yugoslav space, have not been organized due to fear that at this moment it could cause further clashes around who should be allowed to participate.

When it comes to the prospects of dispute resolution, the intersectional feminists did not seem interested in finding a common ground with the radical and moderate feminists. Most of them stated that they do not consider radical feminists to be feminists.

Tara: *“I don't see how you can be transphobic and feminist at the same time. Because if you're a feminist, then you should be against patriarchy. And if you're against transgender people and you're reinforcing patriarchy in order to oppress them. Like for example silencing trans people when they're speaking about violence they experience. You can't be a feminist and reproduce patriarchy!”* (Tr.1: 1356-1360)

Moderate and radical feminists however called for a discussion about their differences and complained that intersectional feminists were silencing their right to freedom of speech.

Center for Civic Courage [in Serbo-Croatian]: *“And yet again, women are forbidden to be critical. We are not allowed to define our own being and who we are. In the past we*

were not allowed to question the religious notion of women, today we are not allowed to question if being a woman is based on a feeling of being a woman.” (Tr.2: 340-342)

Furthermore, radical feminists emphasized that they do not consider anyone an enemy. Intersectional feminists blamed moderate feminists for legitimizing radical feminist discourse that effectively excludes trans women from feminist spaces and ultimately from the feminist movement. While the majority of intersectional feminists hoped that the moderate feminists would rethink their positions on radical feminists, a few considered moderate feminists to be the main threat to the feminist movement.

6. Discussion

In this section, we start by discussing the discourses that we identified and the relationship between them. Then we discuss the generational differences in the feminist movement. Lastly, we discuss how our research participants’ emotions have affected their discursive practices.

Post-Yugoslav Feminist Discourses

We found that moderate feminists shared discursive practices with both radical and intersectional feminists when speaking about the meanings of disputed concepts: ‘feminism’, ‘womanhood’, and ‘safe space’. These discursive practices have led to moderate feminists’ social practices that make the inclusion of trans people in feminist areas a matter of arbitrary decisions rather than the rule. The moderate feminists have positioned themselves in between two very opposed systems of values and norms by insisting on a compromise which legitimizes either stance: the trans inclusionary practices of intersectional feminists and the trans exclusionary practices of radical feminists. The moderate feminists believe that a compromise should be achieved through feminist unity and respectful debate. What is interesting here is that what counts for them as an object for open debate and what does not, varies. Two of the moderate feminists stressed the need for sex workers’ agency and right to talk on their own experiences, but they did not consider extending the same agency to trans people (Tr.1: 2432-2441; 4738-4748). This is particularly important since, as one of our trans research participants noted, trans people have not had much of a voice in the debate about trans people in feminist spaces (Tr.1: 3629-3632). This moderate feminist position

relegates trans people to the object of a debate in which they have little part and no agency. Giving women an authentic voice was a feminist social practice from all three positions, but it was applied to cis women only.

Throughout our literature, interviews and secondary data we found that CWS is more than an organization to the post-Yugoslav feminists (Kahlina, 2006: 55; Miškovska Kajevska, 2017: 43-44; Tr.1: 163-170; Tr.1: 1272-1275; Tr.1: 1603-1625; Tr.1: 2174-2177; Tr.1: 4472-4526; Tr.2: 62-66; Tr.2: 112-119; Tr.2: 227-231; Tr.2: 290-298; Tr.2: 444-451). It represents their shared history, a place where they met regardless of their feminist orientation and most of the feminists, we talked to had been through CWS in one way or another. When an institution so central to their movement became the center of a conflict, it was not just CWS at stake to these activists, it was the meaning of post-Yugoslav feminism as a whole.

Before the appointment of the new director of the Center for Women's Studies (CWS), radical feminists have been dissatisfied with the status quo within the CWS as well (Tr.2: 29-32). The past dissatisfaction is evident from the fact that radical feminists expressed fear over the shrinking spaces of women and how they indicated that there is a tendency in the feminist movement of "*erasing women*" (Tr.1: 3014-3046) – once stated, they were being silenced by accusations of transphobia. Considering the fact that the radical feminists themselves said that they are forming new organizations while their existing organizations are thriving and being platformed at CWS (Tr.1: 3236-3240), we did not find the claims that they are being silenced to be true. We see this situation paralleled in our literature. Pearce et al. (2020) find that radical feminists would talk about being silenced on prime-time national television in the UK while otherwise being continuously platformed (685).

The public support following the appointment for CWS and their new director led intersectional feminists to believe that the radical feminists were forming alliances with moderate feminists who hold the majority within the CWS. On the other hand, the intersectional feminists expressed having had numerous unsuccessful conversations about trans inclusion over a long period (Tr.1: 486-492). It seems that they have been increasingly dissatisfied with CWS leading up to the events surrounding the split. In particular, we noted that intersectional feminists were dissatisfied with the power structures within CWS (Tr.1: 4356-4379). The institution has staff and lecturers who

are employed at universities (Miškovska Kajevska, 2017: 43). The intersectional feminists we talked to were mostly students or former students at CWS. Based on their stories about CWS and the way they talked about the institution (Tr.1: 482-487), we got the impression that they found CWS lectures to be unwelcoming to trans students. Following the appointment of the new director in December 2020, intersectional feminists decided to publicly distance themselves from CWS (Tr.2: 98-101; 154-157; 170-173; 227-231; 271-288; 403-406; 626-629). We interpreted this distancing as a *betrayal worthy of breaking the bonds* within the CWS that are damaging to feminism (Ahmed, 2017: 167). This is a clear representation of a feminist snap (Ahmed, 2017). After the snap, the intersectional feminists started to articulate their interpretations of the meanings of the disputed concepts more precisely through a series of statements that represent our secondary data (Tr.2). This was confirmed by our interviews.

The moderate feminist discourse seemed to mainly work to maintain status quo and resist transformation. According to Fairclough, the interests of hegemonic power are equal to the maintenance of exactly that power and the behavior of moderate feminists is similar in this respect (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 75). We found that intersectional and radical feminists are engaging with moderate discourse at least as much as with each other. We saw radical feminists using the argument that all feminists should be able to have amicable debates about anything, while the intersectional feminists directly opposed this argument. This brought us to the conclusion that the moderate discourse is hegemonic while the radical discourse is aligned with the hegemony. On the other hand, we found intersectional discourse to be an alternative discourse that challenges the hegemony of moderate discourse (Jørgensen & Phillips, 2002: 76).

Generational Tensions in the Post-Yugoslav Feminist Movement

To understand the recently emerged tensions within the feminist movement, we also looked at generational aspects. It is important to stress here that our data does not imply that a particular generation fully matches with a particular feminist discourse.

Our data suggested that there have been three mobilizing factors in the post-Yugoslav space: the Yugoslav Wars in the 90s, the student protests of 2009 against cuts in public spending on higher education, and the 2013 referendum on banning same-sex marriage. Della Porta (2019a) and Chironi (2019) suggest that a political or social crisis mobilizes a large number of young activists

leading to tensions with older generations over ideas and approaches. For younger generation activists, the events in 2009 and 2013 were obviously formative. This leads us to conclude that the 2013 anti-LGBT referendum could have been one of the mobilizing factors for younger feminists to join the feminist movement in order to advocate for LGBTIQ rights, especially since the 2013 referendum put LGBT rights in the center of the political debate in Croatia at that time (Vučković Juroš et al., 2020: 1539). On the other hand, younger Serbian feminists did not point to any specific event. Unlike the Croatian ones, Serbian younger feminists, especially those who identify as trans, had far more references to global events that inspired them to join the movement (Tr.1: 1219; 1247-1250; 1525-1526). Hines (2019) writes that the internet and social media is a significant resource for the trans community since it brings together geographically dispersed people (149). We found that the majority of younger feminists in our sample embraced intersectional feminism since they joined the movement through protests in 2009 and 2013 that were related to women's rights, LGBTIQ rights, and the future of the welfare state.

The older generations of feminists have all mentioned the Yugoslav Wars as a reference to their activist beginnings or the reason they joined the feminist movement. Most of the Croatian feminist activists of older generations had a positive attitude towards the way the feminist movement was organized in the 90s. Both Serbian and Croatian feminists of the older generation were most concerned for women victims of male (sexual) violence. Although most of them did show concern over LGBTIQ rights, they all eventually prioritized the fight against (sexual) violence aimed at women. To understand this position, we turn to Miškovska Kajevska (2017) who writes that the 90s post-Yugoslav feminists, especially those who come from the so-called anti-nationalist side, as is the case for our participants, conceptualize the Yugoslav Wars as a sexual war against women (2-3). Most of the beneficiaries of their work in the 90s were women survivors of sex war crimes (ibid.). Furthermore, some of the older generation feminists believed that social media harms the feminist debates by implying that debates are now hateful and uncivilized because they are happening online and not in the safe feminist spaces (Tr.1: 2458-2461; 2651-2665). It seems that the 90s war has had a strong impact on older feminist generations and their priorities for the movement. The older generation feminists in our sample are all either moderate or radical. Although our data showed that feminists of all generations agree that the male violence is a great concern at the moment, the younger generation feminists seemed to include a much wider group of people whose rights should be advocated for.

Gender Discomforts and Feminist Fears

While conducting the interviews, we found that certain topics elicited emotional responses in some of our research participants. Radical and most moderate feminists were uncomfortable discussing trans people. They would talk a lot, switch around terminology and pronouns or they would entirely avoid the topic. However, discomfort took radical- and moderate feminists to different places.

For the moderate feminists, it mostly seemed like they did not fully understand the topic even though they wanted to. However, their all-around good intentions did not prevent them from reiterating some unfortunate points. In trying to placate her discomfort, one research participant told us about an encounter with a trans woman (Tr.1: 4801-4874). The story was filled with the trans woman's trauma as well as details about her medical transition. Our research participant seemed to replace her discomfort with pity. We found that this resulted in two things. Firstly, it gave off a rather dehumanizing effect where the trans woman became an object of her curiosity rather than a person with a whole life. The only way she was able to understand that someone would want to transition was through a trans person's suffering. This enforces an idea that trans people need to suffer to be trans or to deserve respect. Secondly, this way of portraying trans women as victims of nameless violence, allowed the moderate feminists to remove themselves from the equation of trans oppression. Their ability to transform their discomfort into pity and observe it all from a distance came from the fact that they are not affected by trans people being oppressed. This means that they can take their discomfort up and put it away as convenient and they are not forced to confront it. Since they have emotionally distanced themselves from the situation, it is natural for them to insist that everyone should just get along despite their 'differences' without realizing the harm in this.

The radical feminists felt that the discomfort they were experiencing was something that was unfairly inflicted on them by an outside party. They seemed to interpret any challenge to their argument that women's oppression comes first as oppression. Whenever the radical feminists seemed uncomfortable, the discomfort was quickly followed by anger or indignation. As cis feminists, these radical and moderate feminists exist in spaces that are comfortable for them. It seems their comfort has so far been sustained by the relative invisibility of trans people in the

movement (Ahmed, 2014: 148-149). Now, the environment they used to fit into is rapidly changing, which is why they are experiencing discomfort. This might also be why the intersectional feminists are not expressing discomfort. For them, trans inclusion is not new, it has always been a part of their environment. What is changing for intersectional feminists is not their environment but their perception of people they used to consider friends and comrades.

The discomfort of the radical feminists very quickly led to fear and fear inducing discourses. They seemed to feel that acknowledging trans women as women would mean losing their own womanhood. They responded to the fear by sorting things into the way they understand the world: the (male) oppressor and the oppressed. Without explicitly claiming that trans women are not women, they still manage to equate trans women with male violence through female vulnerability. Ahmed (2014) argues that women are constructed as vulnerable to restrict their mobility (69-70). However, radical feminists use this construction of female vulnerability for their own purposes. While all our participants agree that sexual violence against women is a alarming issue in the post-Yugoslav space, the radical feminists used this to construct the female body as under threat and the male body as threatening. They continue to construct women only spaces as places where women are particularly open to danger, and a place where even the implication of something male can be triggering. Trans women then, through their perceived proximity to maleness, are a threat to cis women's sense of safety, which, since women are the first oppressed class, justifies their exclusion from women only spaces. A noticeable difference between the discourses found in the literature and in our study is that the post-Yugoslav radical feminists we talked to did not actually construct trans women as a threat as has been done in the UK and US (Hines, 2019: 84; Jones & Slater, 2020: 839).

Noticeably, when radical feminists attempted to sort between women, they considered cis women as women but not trans women. To do that, they reiterated biological and classificatory gender essentialist discourses. They defined women through their biological difference from men. They emphasized the threat from men by pointing out their superior physical strength, implying that women are weaker. As we recognized in the literature (Jones & Slater, 2020: 844), this way of defining women often ends up making spaces inaccessible for everyone who does not look traditionally feminine, particularly butch women. They then continue to describe experiences that they consider inherent to womanhood, experiences that are centered around sexism and

discrimination. However, the experiences of oppression they equated with *womanhood* were experiences they shared with our trans woman research participant. The way radical feminists turn to essentialist discourses when threatened reminds us of the way fear makes people turn towards home (Ahmed, 2014). Gender essentialist values become a home for radical feminists: a place to unite that is necessary for the survival of their womanhood. Such course of reasoning narrows down the category of womanhood to white, non-disabled, cis and, for our research participants sometimes, heterosexual category (Jones & Slater, 2020: 837).

We found that the emotions of cis feminists hold the power to restrict the mobility of trans people in feminist spaces. As Koyama (2006) argues, when radical feminists rank female oppression above all other types of oppression, they give themselves a free pass to ignore their own privileges (702). It also allows them to understand their feelings of discomfort and fear as oppression, which in turn makes them feel justified in placating those feelings by oppressing trans women. At the same time, the moderate feminists' discomfort, and their way of dealing with those feelings, could be very uncomfortable to trans people. It could be argued that cis discomfort and trans discomfort are the same, but it is important to realize the power structures at play. Cis women feminists largely dominate the feminist movement, and the moderate feminists are able to distance themselves from their discomfort. However, the thing that these feminists are uncomfortable with is trans people existing in their spaces. Trans people are unable to put away their transness. The fact that some moderate feminists regain their comfort by recounting tales of trans suffering to justify trans existence, gives the impression that they are not willing to confront their discomfort while enforcing a social practice where trans people are required to provide evidence of their existence. However, existing in a space in which your existence needs to be evidenced becomes a form of violence (Ahmed, 2016: 26). Secondly, as both Ahmed (2014) and one of our research participants note (Tr.1: 548-565), discomfort holds the potential for transformation (154). If these feminists were willing to confront themselves and ask the question 'why am I uncomfortable right now?', they might be able to achieve more inclusive feminist spaces.

7. Conclusion

The events following the appointment of the new director at the Center for Woman Studies in Croatia in December 2020 caused a split within the feminist movement in post-Yugoslav space. This split as well as ongoing tensions surrounding gender discourses are evident among feminist organizations, within some organizations and among research participants. We collected statements from feminist organizations and interviewed 12 feminists (2 radical, 3 moderate and 7 intersectional) from Croatia and Serbia about the events and analyzed their discourses. We found that the feminist discourses in the post-Yugoslav space revolve around the meaning of the concepts: ‘feminism’, ‘womanhood’, and ‘safe space’. Radical feminists consider feminism to be specifically the fight against male violence. For moderate feminists, feminism is the fight for equality between genders, and for intersectional feminists, the goal of feminism is the liberation from all types of oppression and exploitation. Intersectional and moderate feminist agree that womanhood is a matter of self-identification. Radical feminists reiterate gender essentialist ideas, arguing that women are born women (biological gender essentialism) or that women are created through shared experiences inherent to womanhood (classificatory essentialism). All three discourses disagree about the role of safe spaces. Intersectional feminists believe all feminist spaces should be safe for everyone, where moderate feminists believe that decisions about the access to safe spaces depends on the function of those spaces. Radical feminists insist on separated spaces for women because trans women implicate maleness which implicates a threat. They hold that women’s oppression comes before all other feminist considerations, therefore *trans exclusionary women only spaces* are necessary to shield women from the male violence. The discursive practices of radical feminists, but also to some degree moderate feminists, surrounding these issues leads to exclusionary social practices towards trans people.

Similarly, discomfort and fear caused by a feeling that the world is changing led moderate and radical feminists to push discourses that are harmful to trans people. One such discourse is the idea that trans lives should be explained through trans suffering (e.g., being trans is so hard that no one would choose it), which can quickly evolve into broadcasting trans trauma, but also reiterates the idea that trans lives need explaining in the first place. Another is when some feminists proclaim that trans women are associated with maleness, which functions both to discursively distance trans women from ‘true’ womanhood, but also to erase the fact that trans women are at least as victimized by male violence as cis women. We found that there is a connection between radical feminists’ feelings of discomfort and fear and their use of gender essentialist discourse. Gender

essentialism provides a binary way to understand gender, which in turn gives these feminists clear boundaries in which they can feel safe, and which are easily defensible.

Furthermore, the situation with CWS has brought up generational tensions between the feminists who mobilized during the Yugoslav Wars (to protect women against the sexual violence during war), and the younger feminists who mobilized within the last decade (for social and economic justice of a wider group of people). The injustices that made them feminists are different, which makes it plausible that they would react differently to the same situation. If these feminists of different generations could see each other's point of departure, they might be able to see that their goals do not have to be conflicting.

The way gender discourses have played out in the post-Yugoslav feminist spaces in recent months have caused a feminist snap that spans across feminist organizations as well as activists' interpersonal relationships. Friendships have ended and organizations are allying themselves against each other. It was not just the appointment of the new director at CWS and her following acts, it was the symbolic value of CWS as a place that creates and spreads feminist knowledge in post-Yugoslav space that made the situation so important. Simmering tensions were brought to the surface, the discourse has poured out in the public space, and it is likely that the snap has permanently changed post-Yugoslav feminist movement. We argue that to become a truly inclusive movement, feminists need to embrace more underprivileged perspectives, including those of trans people. They must face their feelings of discomfort and fear and address them instead of using them as an excuse to exclude trans people from feminist spaces and activism.

To further research on this topic, we have two suggestions. Firstly, we suggest a historical exploration of trans history in the post-Yugoslav space with a focus on the relationship between feminism and trans people. This would help us understand the contemporary feminist movements as well as possibly highlight moments of transfeminist solidarity in the past. Secondly, we suggest a qualitative study to explore what trans activists want from the feminist movement, and what they think trans-inclusive feminism looks like. The key to either of these suggestions, as well as to promote trans-inclusive feminist spaces, is to uplift trans voices and trans agency.

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Annexes

Annex 1 - Research Team Positionalities

Marko: I am a male-bodied, queer person born to a lower-middle-class family, in a country formerly known as Socialist Yugoslavia. My relationship with feminism began when I served my civil service alternative to military service in a radical feminist organization for women victims of domestic violence. Afterwards I was empowered to become a queer activist. My position in this research is of an insider-outsider because I consider myself feminist activist from the post-Yugoslav space. Although my feminist journey started with radical and lesbian feminism, I now identify with intersectional queer-feminism. I believe in the collective activist engagement of all people in fighting multiple forms of oppression and exclusion to change social reality for all of us.

Pernille: I am a queer, cis woman born to the academic middle class in Denmark. I started working with feminism when I became an activist in a Danish organization called Socialist Youth Front (Socialistisk Ungdomsfront/SUF), where I helped found a self-organized, separatist queer group within that organization. I left SUF since it was very male-dominated and queering the organization started to feel like a Sisyphean task when it was barely feminist. However, the experience shaped me and the direction I have taken my studies in. I consider myself a queer feminist. Within this research, I am an outsider. I believe that as a feminist it is my duty to uncover and understand my privileges as much as it is to fight for my own rights. This means I spend a lot of time listening to people with different experiences and intersections than mine.

Annex 2 - Interview Guide

General guidelines

The following guide includes 12 general questions which provide interviewers general guidance for discussion with research participants. The general questions are assigned in numerical order. The interviewers will ask all 12 questions in this document to cover the relevant topics we found in the literature review and theory. The last question is a self-designed question and research participants can raise it and answer it. Interviewers can then ask the self-designed questions to other research participants.

The abcd-assigned questions are follow-up questions that were prepared in advance. Interviewers can ask them if research participants have not answered them already.

Generally, the interviewers will made-up follow-up questions on-spot, depending on the context of the conversation.

Before we start asking questions, we will again present our project, ethical considerations, and general guidelines for the interviewers. Interviewers will again ask for consent for audio-recording. This will help us to set up the interview.

Interview Questions

1. Can you tell us something about your identity and your relationship with feminism?
 - a. What is your educational background? Are you currently employed?
 - b. How and when you got involved with feminist movement?
 - c. What does feminism mean to you?
 - d. What does radical feminism mean to you?
2. How do you think the feminist movement has changed in the last decade or so?
3. Do you think there is a split in the feminist movement? Please explain.
 - a. Is the movement weakened because of this split?
4. What are the greatest threats for the feminist movement today?
 - a. What are the greatest strengths of the feminist movement today?
5. What is a *woman* to you?

- a. What does gender mean to you?
 - b. How do you understand the difference between gender and sex?
 - c. Do you think certain experiences are tied to womanhood?
6. What do you think about women-only spaces and organizations?
 - a. Who is allowed to enter a women-only space?
 - b. Do you think there is a need for women-only spaces/organizations?
7. What are some main concerns of women at this moment?
 - a. **[In case they go outside of the post-Yugoslav space]:** How about in Croatia and/or Serbia?
 - b. What are some main concerns of trans people at this moment?
 - c. **[In case they go outside of the post-Yugoslav space]:** How about in Croatia and/or Serbia?
8. For what do you think the feminist movement should fight? And for whom?
9. How would you describe the relationship between feminist and LGBTIQ movement?
 - a. Do you think these two movements are inherently connected or are there divisions? Are these divisions recent or have they always been there?
10. What do you think about the recent appointment of the new director of the Centre for Women's Studies Zagreb and about what happened after that?
 - a. Has this affected your life in any way?
 - b. Have you lost or gained new friends, colleagues, or acquaintances since the public debate on this appointment?
 - c. What does the term *TERF* mean to you?
 - i. Intuitive questions: Have you ever been called *TERF*?
11. Have you ever been excluded from a feminist space for any reason?
12. How do you understand misogyny?
13. **[Self-designed question]:** **Here we would like you to raise any questions you consider important for this research. Please answer this question at the interview yourself as well.**

Annex 3 - Recruitment Letter

English version:

Dear *[name]*,

We are students from Roskilde University conducting a research project on feminist discourses about gender and trans people in the feminist movement in the post-Yugoslav space. [In case of recruitment through a gatekeeper, add]: We have been referred to you by [name].

This research is a part of our bachelor project and we would like you to collaborate with us and to help us to build on the feminist knowledge about gender discourses in the feminist movements in the post-Yugoslav space. We believe that your experiences with the movement and insight will help us to analyze the discourses, as well as to bring more feminist voices to our university since our findings will be shared with other students, our professors, lecturers, and supervisors.

*If you would like to participate in the research, with your consent we would then ask you to share about 1 hour of your time for an audio-recorded online interview. The interview will consist of open-ended questions about your views on gender, sex, identity, and the current struggles of the feminist movement, and about your experiences, past/current relationships within the feminist movement. We can send you the questions and topics of the discussion in advance. The interview will be scheduled at a time and that is most convenient for you and it will be conducted online via Microsoft Teams, Skype, Zoom, or Google Meet **between April 19 and April 30, 2021**. If you prefer using some other video conference platform apart from the above-mentioned, please let us know.*

We would prefer the interview to be conducted in English, however one of us does speak the local language. The questions are going to be asked by a member of the project team while the other one is taking notes. If you prefer, you can request that only a female researcher is present during the entire interview.

Your participation in this research will be anonymous and we will not disclose any information that could reveal your identity. If you are working or affiliated with a feminist organization, we would not link your statements to the organizations.

If you have questions about our research, please do not hesitate to ask any questions.

This research is conducted under the supervision of Christel Stormhøj from the Department of Social Sciences at the Roskilde University. If you are interested in participating, we will also send you a copy of a consent form.

Thank you for your consideration of participating in our research! We greatly appreciate your help and look forward to talking to you.

[Choose appropriate] In solidarity / Respectfully,

Pernille Ørup Kristensen

Marko Jurcic

Serbo-Croatian version:

Draga [name],

javljam ti se sa Univerziteta u Roskildeu, Kraljevina Danska, gdje s kolegicom provodim istraživanje o feminističkim diskursima o rodu u feminističkom pokretu na postjugoslavenskom prostoru.

Ovo istraživanje je važno za pisanje našeg završnog rada na preddiplomskom studiju. Željeli/e bismo s tobom ostvariti suradnju kako bismo kroz istraživanje doprinjeli/e razumijevanju feminističkog pokreta u postjugoslavenskom prostoru i izazovima koji su pred nama. Kontaktirali smo tebe jer smatramo da nam zbog svog dugogodišnjeg rada na postjugoslavenskom prostoru možeš pomoći da razumijemo posljednje prijepore koji se vežu uz razumijevanje roda i odnosima feminističkih organizacija sa LGBTIQ pokretom. Želimo također i doprinijeti našem sveučilištu s više feminističkih radova s postjugoslavenskog prostora, budući da će naše istraživanje biti dostupno drugim studenticama i studentima, te profesorima i profesoricama.

Ukoliko želiš sudjelovati u istraživanju koje provodimo, tvoje sudjelovanje biti će anonimno i nećemo koristiti niti jednu informaciju koja bi tvoje izjave mogla povezati sa tom ili organizacijom

za koju radiš. Sudjelovanje u istraživanju bi bilo putem intervjua koji bi trajao sat vremena. Postavili bi ti 10-ak pitanja koji se tiču tvojih stavova o rodu, spolu, i identitetima, te iskustvima sa trenutnim prijemima u feminističkom i LGBTIQ pokretu, te o tvojim prijedlozima sa prevazilaženjem tih prijepora. Pitanja bih ti poslao unaprijed, a intervju možemo dogovoriti za **bilo koji dan između 21. i 30. aprila. Moj predlog je da intervju dogovorimo za petak, 23. aprilia između 11 i 15 sati.** Možemo se spojiti preko Skypea: moj ID je [Skype ID].

Razgovor bi vodili na srpskohrvatskom jeziku, a budući da osim tebe još jedino ja govorim naš jezik, na intervjuu neće biti prisutna moja kolegica. Nadam se da je to u redu s tobom.

Ukoliko imaš bilo kakva pitanja u vezi našeg istraživanja, molim te slobodno nas pitaj.

Ovo istraživanje se provodi pod supervizijom prof. Christel Stormhøj s Odsjeka za društvene znanosti Univerziteta u Roskildeu. Ukoliko pristaješ sudjelovati u istraživanju, poslat ćemo ti i zvanični dokument o sudjelovanju koji sadrži i naše etičke principe.

Puno ti hvala na tvojoj pomoći!

Solidarni pozdravi,

Marko Jurčić

(na znanje kolegici Pernille Ørup Kristensen)

Annex 4 - Primary data: Interview transcripts

We make the interview transcripts available for the supervisor and the exam censor upon their request. You may request access to the transcript by contacting us on email: oyerup@ruc.dk or mjurcic@ruc.dk. We will send you the link to the University provided and secured cloud system (OneDrive).

Please note that transcripts may contain spelling mistakes. The transcripts are anonymized, but are not allowed for sharing to third parties.

One interview is entirely transcribed in Serbo-Croatian language, while other transcripts contain words or phrases that have been translated by the authors of this research project.

The interview transcripts contain line numbers and the following mark-ups:

- **[clarifications and/or translations]** For example: “So I think that it kind of repeats itself, this is like collective *forgottenence* [she means obliviousness].”
- **(uncertain transcriptions)** For example (inaudible)
- **<speaker noises or nonverbal gestures>** For example, <laughs> <long pause> <nodes>
- **EMPHASIS** For example: “And EXACTLY THAT, you see?”

Annex 5 - Secondary Data: Statements of Feminist organization

The selection of 13 statements of feminist organizations is transcribed in the language that they were originally published, Serbo-Croatian or English. The document contains a link to the original source of each statement. These statements were published on social media or websites of the organizations.

Transcript 2: <https://docdro.id/j2k7V7U>

The full collection of textual data contains 36 texts, including 13 statements of feminist organizations. The texts that were not included in our selections that was analyzed were published by the following sources:

- Bilten www.bilten.org - leftist post-Yugoslav non-profit news publisher
- LGB Alliance: www.lgballiance.org.uk - British advocacy group founded in opposition to policies on trans issues
- Novosti: www.portalnovosti.com - public media of Serb community in Croatia
- Slobodni filozofski www.slobodnifilozofski.com - independent leftist magazine founded the students of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Science, University of Zagreb
- VoxFeminae: www.voxfeminae.com - post-Yugoslav feminist non-profit news publisher
- Žene u crnom: www.zeneucrn timer.org/en - antimilitarist (radical) feminist organization

Annex 6 - List of codes

Breakdown the list of codes

1. *Opinions: Intra-movement tensions*
 - 1.1. Sex wok
 - 1.2. Cross-generational tensions
 - 1.3. WHOSE OPINION
 - 1.3.1. Everyone should have their own opinion
 - 1.3.2. Trans people opinions matter
 - 1.4. Identity
 - 1.4.1. WOMAN
 - 1.4.2. TRANS KIDS
 - 1.4.3. Movements
 - 1.4.4. PROFESSIONALIZATION
2. *Opinions: References*
 - 2.1. International references
 - 2.2. HISTORICAL REFERENCES TO CWS
 - 2.3. Referencing each other
3. *Emotions: Vulnerability*
 - 3.1. Fear
 - 3.2. Discomfort
 - 3.3. Violence
 - 3.4. Misogyny
4. *Mobilization: Essentialism*
 - 4.1. Essentialism
 - 4.2. Anti-trans
 - 4.3. TERF
 - 4.4. Separatist spaces
 - 4.5. Simplifications/Reductions
5. *Mobilization: ANTI-ESSENTIALISM*
 - 5.1. Intersectionality
 - 5.2. AGENCY
 - 5.3. Snap!
 - 5.4. EMPOWERMENT
6. *Mobilization: FEMINIST CURRENTS*
 - 6.1. Radical
 - 6.2. Liberal
 - 6.3. Intersectional

Annex 7 - Consent Form

Research on feminist discourses about gender and trans people

You are invited to participate in research on discourses about gender and trans people in the feminist movement in the post-Yugoslav space. Please read this form and ask any questions you may have before agreeing to be part of the research. This study is being conducted by Pernille Ørup Kristensen, and Marko Jurčić, students at Roskilde University.

Background Information: The purpose of this study is to understand the effects of the various discourses on gender and trans people in the feminist movements in the post-Yugoslav space from the standpoint of feminist activists.

Procedures: Individual online interviews. If you agreed to participate in this study, we will schedule an interview with you. Two people from our project group will be talking to you for approximately one hour unless otherwise specified or requested. One person will be asking the 13 questions you received in advance. The interviewer might ask supportive questions. You are invited to raise the final question for yourself and other research participants.

The other researcher will be taking notes and might ask additional questions. If you prefer, you can request that only a female researcher is present during the entire interview.

If the interview is conducted in English, you can freely express some of your thoughts in your native language.

With your permission, we will use a digital voice recorder to document your opinions.

Follow-Up Questions: There may be follow-up questions with approximately 1 to 2 questions that will be sent to you by email within the next 3 weeks.

We will protect your identity and respect your boundaries: We will protect your identity, including removing any data that may indicate your identity from the records and the subsequent bachelor project report. You do not have to answer any of the questions you do not wish to. You can at any time decide to stop the interview and retrieve your participation in this research. We will then not use any of the data that has been recorded.

Confidentiality: The records of this study will be kept secure. We will not include any information that will make it possible to identify you in our written report. Research records will be kept in a locked file on a secure university server; only the two student-researchers mentioned in this consent form will have access to digital recordings. The digital data collected in these interviews will be used for writing our bachelor project report and will be deleted after our defense in June 2021. Our supervisor, Christel Stormhøj, will have access to anonymized transcripts.

Ethical considerations: We apply the principles of honesty, transparency, and accountability detailed in the Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. We also apply feminist ethics by emphasizing that care and responsibility for our research participants comes before the outcomes of this research.

Voluntary Nature of the Study: If you decide to participate, you are free to withdraw at any time and we will not use any of the data for the analysis.

Contacts and Questions: The student-researchers conducting this study are Pernille Ørup Kristensen and Marko Jurčić. You can ask us any questions you have for us at any time: oerup@ruc.dk and mjurcic@ruc.dk.

Our supervisor Christel Stormhøj, Associate Professor at Roskilde University can be reached at ISE Roskilde University, Universitetsvej 1, 26.2, 4000 Roskilde or by email stormhoj@ruc.dk.

You will be given a copy of this form to keep for your records.

By signing this document, I state that:

- I have read the above information.
- I consent to participate in the study.
- I agree that this interview will be audio-recorded and my statements anonymized by changing my first name in the study report.

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Signature of the Interviewers _____

Date _____